

Attitude of Consumers' Towards Organized Retailing: An Empirical Evidence

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Abstract:

An important aspect of the current economic scenario in India is the emergence of organized retail. There has been considerable growth in organized retailing business in recent years and it is poised for much faster growth in the future. Major industrial houses have entered this area and have announced very ambitious future expansion plans. Transnational corporations are also coming to India and set up retail chains in collaboration with big Indian companies. However, opinions are divided on the impact of the growth of organized retail in the country. Concerns have been raised that the growth of organized retailing may have an adverse impact on retailers in the unorganized sector. It has also been argued that growth of organized retailing will yield efficiencies in the supply chain, enabling better access to markets to producers (including farmers and small producers) and enabling higher prices, on the one hand and, lower prices to consumers, on the other

The competitive business environment is putting tremendous pressure on the retailing industry. In addition, customers who have sufficient knowledge about markets, products and/or services, and prices through the Internet are becoming more sophisticated and hold greater expectations than ever before*. On and above the entire world is anguish from fear of depression. In this timid situation it is very important to understand core marketing concepts that address the importance of satisfying customer expectations can hardly be implemented

* P. Dabholakar, D. Thorpe and J. Rentz, A measure of service quality for retail stores: Scale development and validation, *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science* 24(1) (1996) 3–16.

without deep understanding of how a consumer's attitudes form and change. This paper attempt to find out, the effect of consumer attitude and its impact on the certain behavior towards organized retailing.

Key Words: Organized Retailing, Consumer Attitude, demographic conditions

Introduction:

The recent years have witnessed rapid transformation and vigorous profits in Indian retail stores across various categories. This can be contemplated as a result of the changing attitude of Indian consumers and their overwhelming acceptance to modern retail formats. Asian markets witness a shift in trend from traditional retailing to organized retailing driven by the liberalizations on Foreign Direct Investments. For example, in China there was a drastic structural development after FDI was permitted in retailing. India has entered a stage of positive economic development which requires liberalization of the retail market to gain a significant enhancement.

Domestic consumption market in India is estimated to grow approximately 7 to 8% with retail accounting for 60% of the overall segment. Of this 60%, organized retail is just 5% which is comparatively lesser than other countries with emerging economies. In developed countries organized retailing is the established way of selling consumer products.

India is on the radar screen in the retail world and global retailers and at their wings seeking entry into the Indian retail market. The market is growing at a steady rate of 11-12 percent and accounts for around 10 percent of the countrys GDP. The inherent attractiveness of this segment lures retail giants and investments are likely to sky rocket with an estimate of Rs 20-25 billion in the next 2-3 years, and over Rs 200 billion by end of 2010. Indian retail market is considered to be the second largest in the world in terms of growth potential.

Indian organized retail market is growing at a fast pace due to the boom in the **India retail industry**. In 2005, the retail industry in India amounted to Rs 10,000 billion accounting for about 10% to the **country's GDP**. The organized retail market in India out of this total market accounted for Rs 350 billion which is about 3.5% of the total revenues.

Retail market in the Indian organized sector is expected to cross Rs 1000 billion by 2010. Traditionally the retail industry in India was largely unorganized, comprising of drug stores, medium, and small grocery stores. Most of the organized retailing in India have started recently and is concentrating mainly in metropolitan cities.

The growth in the Indian organized retail market is mainly due to the change in the consumers behavior. This change has come in the consumer due to increased income, changing lifestyles, and patterns of demography which are favorable. Now the consumer wants to shop at a place where he can get food, entertainment, and shopping all under one roof. This has given Indian organized retail market a major boost.

Retail market in the organized sector in India is growing can be seen from the fact that 1500 supermarkets, 325 departmental stores, and 300 new malls are being built. Many Indian companies are entering the **Indian retail market** which is giving Indian organized retail market a boost. One such company is the Reliance Industries Limited. It plans to invest US\$ 6 billion in the Indian retail market by opening 1000 hypermarkets and 1500 supermarkets.

Pantaloons is another Indian company which plans to increase its retail space to 30 million square feet with an investment of US\$ 1 billion. Bharti Telecoms an Indian company is in talks with Tesco a global giant for a £ 750 million joint venture. A number of global retail giants such as Walmart, Carrefour, and Metro AG are also planning to set up shop in India. Indian organized retail market will definitely grow as a result of all this investments.

Organized retailing in India has come of age especially during the last decade. The liberalization measures post 1991 fuelled the growth of the industry. Many large chains like the Tata, RPG, Raheja's and the Piramal, to name a few, joined the retail bandwagon and have now started coming out of the red after years of making losses and recovering costs. Over these years Indian retailing has evolved from largely informal and disorganized marketplace to a more corporatized industry (we shall refer to this sector as industry despite the Government's hesitation in granting it the status of one). The organized retailing in India has already shot past the Rs. 200 Bn mark and is expected to achieve Rs. 298 Bn by year 2005 (Source: Vision 2005 Document, KSA-Technopak). India has over 12.5 Mn retail outlets, though most of it is fragmented and unorganised.

The Indian Retailing sector has been largely unorganized in the post independence period, to the most part untouched by corporate business principles. It was only in 1980s when the economy started to be opened, the situation began to change. Companies like Bombay Dyeing, Raymond and Grasim from the textiles sector were the first ones from the corporate world to step into the retailing by opening their own outlets.

Titan's is another successful story of a corporate creating a great retailing concept, by establishing a series of elegant watch showrooms across the country. The post liberalization era witnessed new wave of entrants in the sector with large conglomerates like Tatas, the RPG Group, Rahejas and the Piramals investing in the sector. Various other behemoths of the Indian corporate sector like the Birlas, the Hero Group and Reliance have expressed their intention of joining the Indian retail foray.

Hero Group has recently declared its plan to enter retailing by opening retail stores on the lines of 7-11 Stores. The Birlas have marked their presence by acquiring Madura Garments, while Reliance plans to develop its retail venture and fuel retail network simultaneously. Even the public sector oil companies like HPCL, IOCL and BPCL realized their potential for entering into retailing by leveraging their supply chain network.

Here are the reasons for the corporate sector to enter into retailing: -

- **2nd Most Attractive Retail Market:**

AT Kearney has ranked India as the second most attractive retail market after Russia, in its Global Retail Development Index 2004 report. Going three ranks up and surpassing China, in contrast to last years position, India has achieved the second position despite of stringent FDI rules and regulations. The improvement in living standards and continuing economic growth (40% growth in GDP between 1999 and 2003) has been the major reasons behind international retailers gaining confidence in the Indian retail market. Other reasons include increase in per capita income by one-third between 1999 and 2003 and the market size of the country that offers tremendous promise as its population is expected to surpass China by year 2050.

- **Low Penetration of the Organized Retail Sector:**

The mere 2% share of the organized retail sector in the total Indian retail market worth Rs. 10000 Bn makes it a hot cake for Indian corporate sector. With increasing number of nuclear families, working women, greater work pressure and increased commuting time, convenience has become an integral part of shopping. Customers want all-under-one-roof places to shop that offers them convenience and variety. This offers an excellent incentive to the corporate sector to join the retail bandwagon.

- **Exceptionally High Growth Rate:**

The sector has witnessed spiralling growth rate and will continue with the same for a couple of years. The present size of the organized retail market has shot past the Rs. 200 Bn mark and is expected to touch Rs. 298 Bn by 2005 (Source: Vision 2005 document, KSA-Technopak) and Rs. 372 Bn by year 2007 (ETIG, Changing Gears - Retailing In India).

- **Increase in Consumer Spending and Shift in Consumer Buying Behavior:**

According to KSA-Consumer Outlook 2003 study the consumer spending grew by 12% and that consumer confidence is higher than any other Asia-Pacific market. The consumer spending patterns are changing with the consumers moving beyond basic necessities to acquire trappings of comfort, luxury and style. With higher disposable incomes and easier funding options, the 285 million strong Indian middle-class is creating a retail boom like never before.

- **Improved Living Standards:**

The Global Retail Development Index 2004 has placed India on a higher Country Risk with a score of 62, which is due to increased living standards and continued economic growth. This improvement in living standards has fuelled the desire among shoppers to get the best in terms of product, price, service and satisfaction. Corporate sector companies are in a better position to satiate the customer expectations with shopping satisfaction, entertainment, quality products, polite salespersons, right product information and discounts.

- **Operational Competitive Advantage:**

Having developed strong processes and world-class infrastructure, the corporate sector companies can have the advantage over other retailers who are busy addressing such bottlenecks as supply chain and poor operational efficiency. In its Vision 2005 document, KSA-Technopak has identified this as an opportunity for the entrants with inherent high operational efficiencies.

Analysis

Major goal of this study is to investigate consumers' attitudes towards the emerging of Organized Retailing. The researcher aims at examining agreement/ disagreement cues for determining attitudes. Toward this, we proposed specific research objectives based on the literature in marketing and consumer behavior as follows:

Research Objectives

- ✓ Assess validity and reliability for the developed scale that reflects consumers' attitudes towards emergence of organized retailing.
- ✓ To find out the Consumer's Overall attitude towards Organized Retailing
- ✓ Investigate the relationship between consumers' attitudes towards organized retailing and their demography.

Research Design

To achieve and test the objectives and hypotheses as well as to find answers for the developed research questions, a survey study was undertaken over a three months period during January to March 2007 in various cities of Gujarat with help of designing a simple structured questionnaire.

An attempt was made to gather a sample that was representative of all shoppers by undertaking more interviews at peak shopping times. In practice, the problem of non-response arose since (94 percent) completion questionnaires were returned and unusable for the purpose of analysis. Daytime interviewing lead to high proportions of female respondents

and probably also accounted for relatively high percentage of 64 percent. Nevertheless, it was judged that a reasonably representative sample was obtained.

Data Analysis Procedures

For Assessing validity Cronbach’s Alpha was used. The value of the conbach’s alpha Comes to 0.62.

Table: 1 Cronbach’s Alpha

t number	High Sit.		Low Sit.		T. Test	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	T.	sig.(*)
1	3.83	0.92	2.52	1.36	9.43	0.00
2	3.35	1.62	2.58	1.28	5.35	0.00
3	3.29	1.17	2.62	1.20	4.78	0.00
4	3.69	0.98	2.18	0.90	13.58	0.00
5	3.03	1.31	2.29	1.11	5.10	0.00
6	3.51	1.03	1.86	0.86	14.71	0.00
7	3.63	1.16	2.02	1.02	12.40	0.00
8	3.41	1.04	2.06	0.99	11.04	0.00
9	3.53	0.95	1.91	0.89	14.82	0.00
10	3.37	1.25	2.99	1.22	2.62	0.00
11	3.40	1.02	1.89	0.95	12.85	0.01

It is important to mention here that such result might be due to the nature of this study, which handled a new phenomenon in the market. The availability of organized retailing has recently emerged.

Hypotheses 1

Null Hypo	There are no significant differences among consumers' attitudes toward organized retailing.
Alternate Hypo	There are significant differences among consumers' attitudes toward organized retailing.

The calculated value of Chi-Square is 15.623 which is much lower than 36.415 with 24 degrees of freedom and 5% significance level, which indicates that, the null hypothesis is true stating “there are no significant differences among consumers’ attitude towards organized retailing.” This could be because organized retailing is at its blossoming stage.

Hypotheses 2

Null Hypo	Demographic conditions do not affect the attitudes of the consumers towards organized retailing and their demography.
Alternate Hypo	Demographic conditions affect the attitudes of the consumers towards organized retailing and their demography.

In this hypothesis various demographic variables are taken i.e. age, income, etc. and then are tested for any differences. The calculated value of the Chi – Square is 38.452 which is higher than the table value of the same with 24 degrees of freedom and 5% significance level i.e. 36.415. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternate hypothesis is accepted stating “Demographic conditions affect the attitudes of the consumers towards organized retailing and their demography”. This indicates that the demographic conditions play a vital role in deterring the pattern of consumer attitude towards organized retailing.

Conclusions:

How close we have reached in creating Indian Retail Miracle that every one hopes is just around the corner. It is considered opinion of this writer that the threats and weaknesses need to be highlighted for in handling of those lie the biggest of the opportunities sought by Organized Retail. While we do that, we must appreciate that Indian Consumer is still learning to deal with Organized Retail and it shows in the fact that as much as 94% (or so) of India's Retail sales still comes from unorganized sector, what is popularly called Mom-n-Pop Stores. The pioneers of Organized Retail are doing a fine job of 'bringing-up the consumers'. Their ratios are significantly higher than that those of their neighbors in the same mall. And this is not just because they are 'Anchor Tenants'. It is because they are paying attention to a wide spread issues that others have conveniently ignored. This applies to those in Fashion and Lifestyle segments too. On one side where Indian consumers are still learning to deal with Organized Retail, the work force too is yet to learn the ropes of this wonder. And that shows in the kind of shopping experience available in the stores.

Many consumers showed their feeling of being cheated many consumers talked about how they were cheated. One of the member said “On all occasions, my experience reminded me of

a legal expression 'caveat emptor'- let the buyer beware! If they (Store) had 20 trays for fresh fruits & vegetables, in at least 9 to 10 the trays old stuff was smartly mixed with the fresh arrivals. The result was if I tried to pick up a lemon, three times out of five I'd either pick up a rotten lemon or my hand touched the wet parts of a rotten lemon. There were two trays filled with beetroot. I had tough time getting 8 good hard pieces out of it. Most of them had gone soft. If I tried to pick nice shining brinjal for making 'Baingan Bhurta', what I got were softened pieces and I began to wonder if those were already roasted and kept there". These shows that still there are many areas for improvement that stores can work in better fashion.

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